

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 2 | APRIL - JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“CURRICULUM CO-CREATION: ENGAGING STUDENTS AS PARTNERS IN CURRICULUM DESIGN”

To ensure the creation of engaging and impactful learning experiences for students, teachers and educational leaders need to properly design a curriculum that best caters to the needs of learners. Curriculum design entails setting clear learning goals, incorporation of innovative learning and strategies, and the development of assessment tools that apply higher order thinking skills. But beyond these expectations, where does the student stand? How can we engage students as partners in educational design? What role do they play in ensuring that the curricula is indeed responsive to their needs and to the needs of the times? Let us ruminate upon this matter and see what the learners and educational system as a whole can gain when we engage students as partners in curriculum design.

Let us look back at the recent history of the curriculum of Philippine education. Philippine educational curriculum during the American occupation from 1900-1935 was heavily influenced by the U.S. education system, emphasizing English language instruction, basic literacy, civic education, and vocational training. As the zeal for Philippine independence grew and deepened among Filipinos, the curriculum evolved to include Filipino identity, culture, and nationalism. As the years pass, bilingual education and the inclusion of values education and Filipino-oriented subjects was pushed.

As more research were conducted and to ensure that Philippine education system is at par with national and international standards, various reforms were initiated. And in 2002, the Philippines implemented the Basic Education Curriculum or BEC. It was a significant reform of the Philippine education system that aimed at

enhancing the quality of basic education by streamlining content, fostering values integration, and promoting student-centered learning. Existing curriculum was redesigned to five learning areas: Filipino, English, Mathematics, Science, and Makabayan, which is an integrative subject encompassing civics, culture, arts, health, and social studies. The new curriculum was meant to decongest the old curriculum, making it more manageable and focused on essential competencies. (Bago, 2001)

Despite its noble goals, various challenges were seen with the BEC 2002. Originally intended to integrate the disciplines mentioned, Makabayan became overloaded with content, potentially weakening its effectiveness. The swift nationwide rollout of the BEC left limited time for adequate teacher training and resource preparation, leading to implementation challenges. Insufficient attention was given to entrepreneurial skills and vocational training. Some educators and policymakers further expressed concerns over the BEC's effectiveness, leading to debates and calls for further review. (Fernandez, 2022)

So, in early 2010, Understanding by Design (UbD) was introduced to the Philippine education system. It was part of efforts to improve instructional planning and student learning outcomes, make teaching more focused on deep understanding and transferable skills, and less focus on rote memorization. Additionally, the Philippines had to adhere to the global shift of education towards competencies-based and performance-based education, and UbD aligned with these trends. UbD emphasized the development of critical thinking and real-world application of knowledge. And teachers were also provided with a structured system in designing lessons that align with learning area objectives, assessments standards, and appropriate instructional activities, thus promoting coherence in teaching. (Garcia & Martinez, 2024)

Nevertheless, many teachers faced challenges in understanding and applying the UbD framework effectively. Due to the swift implementation of the programs, teachers often had difficulty in following through due to insufficient training and support. Also, traditional testing methods remained prevalent despite UbD's emphasis on performance-based assessments, eventually leading to inconsistencies. Eventually, UbD was replaced with the K to 12 Basic Education Program, which was implemented starting in 2012. (Garcia & Martinez, 2024)

The Department of Education of the Philippines considers the K to 12 Basic Education Program as one of the most significant reforms in the country. It aims to provide our learners to provide every student with the chance to obtain a high quality education founded on a simplified, improved curriculum that is similar and acknowledged globally. The curriculum encourages the development of social skills and reduces emotional stress and improves participation by means of performance -based learning. (Calderon, 2014)

In adherence to RA 11476, or the GMRC and Values Education Act of 2020, the formation of the Filipino learners' values and the development of their characters will be intensified under the new curriculum. It will also integrate peace competencies that will highlight the promotion of non-violent actions and the development of conflict-resolution skills in learners, thus the MATATAG Curriculum was borne. The MATATAG Curriculum aims to reduce the number of competencies and to focus more on the development of foundational skills literacy, numeracy, and socio-emotional skills of Kindergarten to Grade 3 learners, thus, decongesting the present K to 12 curriculums. (Catalina, 2024)

In all these curriculums, we can safely conclude that everything our educational leaders and government does and plans is for the development of learners, ingraining them with knowledge and skills they must possess to succeed in life, in order for them to contribute to their community and nation. We always create a

curriculum that is learner centered. But as teachers and educators, have we ever engaged them as partners in educational design? Have we ever considered that they can become partners in curriculum co-creation?

Recognizing students as partners in designing their education seems empowering but has its challenges. Partnering with students makes us question ingrained ideas about information and power structures, which could basically overturn culturally dominant traditions for every student and member of staff. Although collaboration may be encouraged, students frequently have so little say in decisions that it seems like they were merely present to check off a box. This tokenism can reduce the effectiveness of the collaboration by discouraging students from truly participating. The general dearth of tools and assistance for teachers and pupils is a significant obstacle. Communication, negotiation, and design are all crucial talents for co-creating a curriculum, but schools do not encourage or teach these abilities. Teachers and students may feel unsure of their roles in the absence of training.

It cannot be denied that students play several important roles in educational design in a way of having a healthy collaboration and communication between the other learners and the teachers. Students share ideas, suggestions and feedback about their daily learning experiences. For example, teachers may inquire about the expectations of their learners towards a learning area, and the teacher can use that feedback in planning lessons, conducting instruction, and performing assessments. During classroom activities, teachers can engage learners as partners in designing a rubric that demonstrates learner participation and less teacher-interference to allow learners' creativity to flourish. Learners can therefore assist in shaping a curriculum that is more engaging and aligned with their passions, fostering increased motivation and deeper learning by expressing their interests.

Furthermore, the students' direct involvement in curriculum creation fosters critical thinking and inquiry, which advances their intellectual development and problem-solving abilities. Engaging them as partners in curriculum design may help foster a collaborative environment where students and teachers work together and may help enhance communication and mutual respect among teachers, curriculum planners, and students. Additionally, taking into account student input during curriculum evaluations may assist guarantee that the lessons' material stays effective and relevant, enabling ongoing development based on real-world learning experiences. And more importantly, when learners are involved in curriculum decisions, they develop a sense of responsibility and ownership over their education, which hopefully should lead to increased engagement and commitment to learning, thereby fostering a sense of responsibility and ownership for their own learning.

However, engaging students as co-creators of the curriculum can still face challenges. For one, students may lack experience or expertise in the subject matter. Secondly, traditional teacher-student relationships discourage students from expressing their voices. Thirdly, meaningful collaboration between educators and students may require additional time for training, discussion, and consensus-building—resources that are often limited in schools. Fourthly, students come from different backgrounds, interests, and learning styles, which can lead to conflicting ideas about what the curriculum should look like, and this poses diverse and conflicting perspectives. Despite these challenges, with proper guidance, scaffolding, and institutional support, students can become valuable contributors to more inclusive and effective curricula.

What does the future hold then if we engage students as partners in educational design?

The future of curriculum after engaging students as partners in designing curriculum may hopefully become more collaborative, flexible, and responsive to the needs of the Filipino learner. What students share may

help shape in customizing learning experiences that align with interests, goals, and learning styles of students. Teachers may act more as guides and facilitators as education will shift further toward an educational system where they share responsibility. And with student feedback, the relevance of the skills and competencies being taught in real-world contexts may help in ensuring curricula to stay up to date.

In conclusion, challenges may arise as we engage students as partners in educational design, but with proper guidance and scaffolding, they will definitely help in improving and making the curriculum more alive and accessible for all.

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